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BASKETBALL AS A MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Outdoor games are an integral part of the national culture of every nation. Because these games instill motor activity specific to each person, play an important role in his physical and psychological development, and the development of personal qualities. In this regard, outdoor games such as basketball, volleyball, football and so on are not only a factor ensuring the development of the body, but also one of the main means of physical education and sports. Recently, the popularity of basketball in Azerbaijan has been increasing. This is happening as a result of the joint efforts of the National Olympic Committee, the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Azerbaijan and the Azerbaijan Basketball Federation.

Keywords: basketball, outdoor games, exercises, physical education, sports

At the present stage of development of our country, the strategic goal is to achieve the complete and sustainable development of the system of physical education and sports in the country, improve with its help the health of children, adolescents and young people, solve pressing social and economic problems in society and organize activities in accordance with the requirements of the modern era. The main directions in this area are the formation of physical culture and sports activities as a healthy lifestyle in the minds of schoolchildren and students, the achievement of a high level of physical education through the formation of abilities necessary for their physical development and physical improvement, and the development of a creatively thinking citizen and personality. The goal here is to develop in each athlete the physical qualities characteristic of the sport. The games are related to each other in many ways. For example, variety of movements, intensity, change in physical activity, etc. Since this process lasts a long time, the athlete is required to have special endurance, speed, strength, agility, and so on. In connection with the technique and tactics of performing tricks taught for this purpose, special training and its elements, as well as systematized movements, are used in the training process.

In order to organize public health, sports activities are organized and conducted in educational institutions. Such important government work is carried out by physical culture groups created under these organizations. The physical culture team is headed by a council. The council creates divisions for sports including basketball, volleyball, football, handball, in accordance with other local opportunities. In each of these divisions, groups or teams are organized depending on the age, gender and level of training of those involved. In many cases, a group combines 2 teams. Boys and girls are included in groups by age. The training is conducted by the trainer who is responsible for the training of the unit. In each created group, at the general meeting of the unit, a representative of the group is elected, and in

the team - a captain, members of 3-7 people. They participate in organizing their teams, drawing up a general work plan and admitting new members to the unit. They also take part in budgeting, overseeing their training, teams' preparation for competitions, etc.

Basketball, like other sports, began to take its first steps in Azerbaijan in 1920. Basketball gradually became the favorite game of Azerbaijani youth, and for the first time it began to be played in Baku - on the courts of the Government House, the swimming school and sailors of the Caspian Fleet. In 1920, basketball was developed in two sports societies: the Unitas sports club and the physical education society.

Since 1923, the sport of basketball has been included in the program of all complex competitions and sports days, and the mass organization of simple sports grounds for basketball has become the focus of attention of most organizations. It is known that in Baku basketball was in third place in popularity after football and volleyball. The first Baku championship took place in October 1924. Beginning in 1924, basketball teams were organized and games were held not only in the city, but also in the districts.

Since then, teams have been created in individual work collectives, departments and enterprises, higher educational institutions, sports societies, and the number of basketball fans involved in training has increased every day. In 1926, about 300 basketball teams and exercises were registered in Baku alone. This was no accident.

In the 1920-1930s, the strongest basketball team in Azerbaijan grew up in the Demir Yolu sports club. It is no coincidence that the team of this club has been awarded the title of champion of Azerbaijan for several years.

In 1931, the Azerbaijani men's team won the Transcaucasian Championship and for the first time won the right to compete as an independent team at the USSR Championship. Starting from this year, the Azer-

baijani men's team has been leading in the Transcaucasus for a long time, and the level of technical and tactical training of our athletes is being modernized and modernized every year.

Since 1934, the republican basketball championship was held for the first time. This was due to the development of basketball in other cities and regions besides Baku. The national teams of Baku, Ganja and Khanlar performed at these competitions. The team of the Baku society "Dynamo" was awarded the name of the first champion of the country. Let's also assume that this company maintained this leadership for the next five years in a row.

As a result of the wide spread of basketball in Azerbaijan and the training of talented basketball players in our republic, starting in 1935, the Azerbaijani national team began to successfully compete in the USSR Championship. From the same year, the women's team of our republic began to test their strength in the USSR championship competitions. The following year, 1936, it can be felt that there has been a significant improvement in the technical and tactical skill of our team, and the results of the official meetings held by both teams can once again prove this. Basketball teams have played approximately 100 international matches. Our republic's men's basketball team was especially strong, winning the right to play in the major league several times.

The spread and development of basketball in Azerbaijan is associated with the name of the Honored Coach of the USSR, Professor T. Abasov, and this talented coach devoted his entire adult life to the noble cause of the development and flourishing of basketball.

Azerbaijani basketball, which experienced stagnation at the end of the twentieth century, entered a new stage of development under the influence of the victories of Azerbaijani athletes at the Olympic Games. The Azerbaijan Basketball Federation (ABF) was created in 1992. Z. Salakhova was elected as the first president of the ABF, and under his leadership, the Azerbaijan Basketball Federation (ABF) was accepted as a full member of the International Basketball Federation (FIBA) in 1994, which gave our team the right to compete in international competitions. competitions under the flag of our independent state. In order to ensure their mass participation, a southern regional branch of the ABF was created in Jalilabad, and a regional center of the ABF was created in Ganja. Thanks to raising international relations to a new level, as a result of the work

done by ABF, Azerbaijani basketball players, starting in 2000, began to regularly participate in international competitions. The Azerbaijani national team participated in this tournament. A representative of the Azerbaijan Basketball Federation was elected a member of the BTBL Council.

Recently, the popularity of basketball in Azerbaijan has been increasing. This is happening as a result of the joint efforts of the National Olympic Committee, the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Azerbaijan and the Azerbaijan Basketball Federation. On their initiative, since 2002, Lithuanian Rimas Kurtinaitis, Olympic champion, world and European champion, has been invited to train our team at the world level. With the arrival of R. Kurtinaitis in Azerbaijan, a new stage in the development of basketball began, and the number of basketball players is increasing every day. He won gold medals at the IV Islamic Solidarity Games held in Baku.

Thus, outdoor games develop speed, agility, speed, and create the basis for physical improvement (especially in a competitive form). The game teaches people how to behave in a team, instills the skills to subordinate their personal interests to the common good. It also teaches one to be strong-willed and skillful, and teaches one to act correctly and independently. Play is also a means of education; it helps the development of speech and intelligence, increases initiative, and affects cheerfulness and dexterity. Outdoor games have been used at all times in accordance with people's lifestyles. In the 17th century, educators realized that these games played a big role in the learning and physical and mental development of children and believed that these games should be widely used in education.

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